

Dataset 1: Dalton rain catchment reservoir



Dataset 1: Ein Afek reserve - Spring water



Dataset 2: Dor aquaculture facility - Spring water



Precipitation (mm)



Scale Bar 200m

Exact location of sampling

Dataset 3: Lake Kinneret - Freshwater



Dataset 1: Reshafim fish pond - Spring water



Dataset 1: Timorim (left and right) - Wastewater



Dataset 1: Yerucham - Rain catchment pond

